

Electrochemical investigations on some hydrazones

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The electrochemical behaviour of 3-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-diones has been studied over a wide pH range at dropping mercury and glassy carbon electrodes. These aryl hydrazones give one four-electron wave/peak corresponding to the reduction of hydrazono group. The wave/peak is found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible in nature. A reduction mechanism is suggested for the aryl hydrazones.

The redox behaviour of hydrazones^{1,2} attracted considerable attention due to their importance as precursors of various antineoplastic and antidiabetic compounds. The reduction of aryl hydrazones has been reviewed by Turyan³. Some workers reported four-electron reduction of hydrazones in acidic as well as in alkaline medium with the formation of amino compound⁴. But Fahmy *et al*⁵ reported further reduction of amino compound formed after four-electron reduction to ammonia and ketone by two-electron wave.

In view of the discrepancies existing in the redox behaviour of hydrazones, we have selected some 3-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-diones (I) (SHPAD) for a comprehensive study taking into consideration some pertinent aspects of redox phenomenon such as nature of the wave, characterisation of end-products and mechanism of electrode process.

where R represents substituent (Table 1)

Results and Discussion

Under the experimental conditions, the electrochemical reduction of SHPADs was found to be dependent on the pH. A single, four-electron cathodic wave was observed in the entire pH range 2.5–12.0. However, an additional two-electron wave was observed at pH > 4.5. Polarographic characteristics are incorporated in Table 1. The first wave has been assigned to the reduction of hydrazono group⁶ and the second two-electron wave, observed at higher pH, may be assigned to the reductive splitting of the C–N bond, which is possible due to the presence of activating >C=O group

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics of 3-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-diones

pH = 4.5, concn = 1.0×10^{-4} M

Sl no	R	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$ V/pH	i_d μA	αn	$I \times 10^{-2}$	K_{fh}° $cm\ s^{-1}$
1	H-	0.82	0.11	0.84	0.36	41.55	6.2×10^{-5}
2		0.88	0.10	0.72	0.36	35.62	2.3×10^{-5}
3		0.82	0.10	0.92	0.43	45.51	7.2×10^{-6}
4		0.84	0.12	1.12	0.32	55.41	1.2×10^{-6}
5		0.84	0.11	1.04	0.36	51.45	1.2×10^{-6}

on both sides of carbon atom of the C-N bond.

Both the waves were found to be diffusion-controlled by the linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ and i_d vs concentration. Shift in the half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) towards negative side with increasing pH of the solution, indicates the irreversible nature of the waves⁷. Irreversibility is further established by plots of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$, the slope of which exceeded $0.0591/n$. The value of αn (the product of transfer coefficient and number of electrons transferred in the rate determining step) and p (number of protons involved in the rate determining step) were determined by using expression^{7,8},

$$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = \frac{0.0517}{\alpha n}$$

$$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH} = \frac{0.0591}{\alpha n} p$$

Cyclic voltammograms of SHPADs were recorded at different scan rates and with different concentrations in the pH range 2.5–12.0. All the hydrazones exhibited a four-electron cathodic peak in that pH range, which was found to be diffusion-controlled⁹ by the linear plots of i_p vs concentration and i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ passing through the origin. However, at higher pH (>4.5), an additional peak appeared at more negative potentials which is assigned to the reductive cleavage of amino compound formed. No corresponding anodic peak was observed in the reverse scan, indicating the irreversibility of electrode reaction. However, at far off positive side, a small hump was observed which is independent of scan direction. It indicates that the hump is due to the oxidation hydrazones. The anodic peak was found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible in nature.

CPE of SHPADs was carried out at a potential slightly higher than the reduction potential of the second peak, the number of electrons consumed in the electrode process was found to be six (Table 2). The end-products were identified by the TLC and two products were found to be sulphanilamide (II) (by comparison with standard sulphanilamide) and 4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione (III) [IR peak at 3210 (NH_2), 2650 (C-H) and 1695 cm^{-1} (CO)].

Redox mechanism : On the basis of polarography, cyclic voltammetry, CPE and spectral analysis, the mechanism proposed for the reduction of SHPADs is presented in Scheme 1.

This mechanism is supported by the shift of $E_{1/2}$ and E_p towards more negative side with the increase in pH of the solution, as protons are consumed in the reduction of hydrazono group. This mechanism corroborates the work of others^{2,10} for the reduction of aryl hydrazones.

Table 2. Values of n determined by coulometry and composition of products in preparative controlled potential reduction of 3-(4-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-diones at glassy carbon electrode

pH	E (applied potential)	Values of n from coulometry	Products
2.5	-1.00	4.10	Sulphanilamide (II) Aminoketone (III)
4.5	-1.00	4.15	Sulphanilamide (II) Aminoketone (III)
6.2	-1.50	6.20	Sulphanilamide (II) 4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione (IV) ammonia
10.5	-1.50	6.15	Sulphanilamide (II) 4-phenylaminobutane-2,4-dione (IV) ammonia

Scheme 1

Based on the identification of the product reduced in the second two-electron reduction peak at pH >4.0 for these compounds and on the detection of the products of the controlled potential electrolysis, i.e. 1-aminophenylbutane-1,3-dione (IV) and ammonia, it can be concluded that the second two-electron peak is due to the reduction of activated C-N bond. This was further confirmed by recording cyclic voltammograms of (III) separately under similar experimental conditions. Similar behaviour has been reported by other workers² for compounds having activated C-N bonds.

A small anodic peak at far off positive potential has been assigned to the two-electron oxidation of hydrazono group

at glassy carbon electrode. The oxidation of hydrazono group has been postulated as presented in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

This oxidation reaction also supports the work of other workers¹¹

Experimental

Polarographic measurement was made on an Elico DC CL-25 polarograph. Potentiometric studies were carried out on a DP 510 pH-meter with glass electrode. All potentials reported are with reference to SCE. Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out on a BAS-CV-27 instrument using a three-electrode cell – glassy carbon as working electrode, SCE as reference electrode and Pt-wire as an auxiliary electrode.

Hydrazono derivatives of sulphonamides (Table 1) were synthesised by literature method¹². The stock solutions (1.0×10^{-3} M) of all these compounds were prepared in purified DMF. An aqueous 1.0 M KCl (A.R.) solution was used as the supporting electrolyte. Britton-Robinson (BR) buffers were used for maintaining the pH. Solutions for polarographic and cyclic voltammetric measurements were prepared by mixing solution of the compound (1 ml), DMF (2 ml), KCl solution (1 ml) and BR buffers (6 ml) of varying pH.

Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) was carried out at glassy carbon electrode. For this purpose, depolarizer (2 ml), BR buffer (4 ml), DMF (3 ml) and KCl solution (1 ml) were electrolysed by the application of potential slightly higher than the reduction potential of hydrazono group. From the decrease of current with time during electrolysis, the number of electrons transferred were calculated. Progress

of electrolysis was monitored by recording voltammograms at different intervals of time, until only background current was realised. Number of electrons involved in the electrode process was evaluated by coulometry. Value of Q was read directly, and by the application of formula, $Q = nFN$, the number of electrons (n) were calculated.

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